

FACTOR OF DEVELOPING FUTURE TEACHERS LIFE SKILLS BASED ON ANALYSIS OF FIRST-TIME EXPERIENCE ABROAD

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Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda zamonaviy jamiyatda bo'lajak pedagoglarning asosiy vazifalaridan biri o'z kasbiy kompetentligi va intellektual salohiyatining yuqoriligi, sadoqatliligi, g'oyaviy e'tiqodliligi, o'z kasbini sevishidir. Xalqaro tajribalar asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarni o'quvchilarda hayotiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar vazifalar to'g'risidagi fikr mulohazalar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: bo'lajak pedagoglar, yangi taraqqiyot, zamonaviy dunyoqarash, ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar, uzluksiz ta'lim, individual sifatlar, barkamol inson, ta'lim standartlari, fuqarolik jamiyatini, ilmiy-metodik.

Abstract: In this article, one of the main of future pedagogues in modern society today is the high level of their professional competence and intellectual potential, loyalty, ideological conviction, and love for their professional. Based on international experience, these are presented ideas and considerations about the tasks of future pedagogues in the formation of like skills in students.

Key words: future pedagogues, new development, modern wordview, scientific theoretical views, continuous education, individual qualities, a harmonious person, educational standards.

Based on the analysis of foreign experience, in the research conducted by the world's leading higher educational institutions and scientific centers on the preparation of future teachers for innovative activities, the implementation of modern education, special attention is paid to the introduction of international educational standards, criteria for the professional skills of future teachers, the problems of creating an innovative educational environment. In this regard, scientific research aimed at expanding the pedagogical competence of young teachers based on such indicators as motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive and self-assessment of the successful use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in the educational process plays an important role [1, p. 12]. In our country, research is being carried out on the modernization of the modern educational content of training future young teachers for the continuous education system based on advanced foreign experiences, on the creation of an educational environment aimed at creating the necessary conditions for students to realize their internal potential. The Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan sets out such priority tasks as "further improving the continuous education system, increasing the opportunities for quality educational services, and continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market". In this regard, improving the pedagogical system for the formation of an educational environment aimed at developing life skills in students of future teachers is of great importance.

That is why today we are repeatedly discussing the ideas about teacher competence. In all pedagogical and psychological literature, the word "competence" is given a specific meaning, which is taken from the English "competence" - understood, capable. In content, it means the concept of "effective use of theoretical knowledge in activity, the ability to demonstrate high professional qualifications, skills and talents".

The reforms taking place in our republic today are directly related to the innovative education system.

Today's teacher must be proactive in dealing with his students, have organizational skills, always be energetic, enthusiastic, and confident in his own strength and capabilities. Professional In order to be competent, one should pay attention to the following [2, p. 28]: a) a creative approach to professional activity; b) be active in creating new ideas;

c) collaboratively exchange ideas on pedagogical achievements, study advanced pedagogical experiences. The teaching profession requires great mental and physical strength, therefore, significant requirements are also imposed on the health of the teacher.

The teacher should have well-developed vocal cords, good eyesight, be able to stand upright for a long time, and be able to communicate well with students. The great thinker Abu Ali Ibn Sino also gave advice on the teacher's speech hygiene in his work "The Canons of Medicine": "Shouting loudly for a long time requires a large amount of air to be exhaled. Both of these are dangerous." All the reforms taking place in society, the advancement of education to new levels, the rapid development of science and technology, and most importantly, the creation of creative and presidential schools in our country, are also innovations in the education system. Also, today's teacher is not only a teacher, but also an educator. In order to explore the existing opportunities for developing socio-cultural competence in students, the DTS and qualification requirements for primary education were studied, taking into account modern approaches to the process of training future teachers. The general requirements for the level of training of future teachers in the field of education are as follows [3, p. 18]: to have systematic knowledge related to worldview and social processes; to know the basics of the humanitarian and natural sciences, current issues of current state policy, to be able to independently analyze social problems and processes; to know the history of the Motherland, to be able to express and scientifically substantiate one's opinion on issues of cultural, national and universal values, to have an active life perspective based on the idea of national independence; to have a holistic view of the processes and phenomena taking place in nature and society; to know the legal, as well as spiritual, cultural criteria that determine a person's attitude to another person, society and the environment, and to be able to take them into account in professional activities; know the methods of collecting, storing, processing and using information, be able to make independent decisions in their professional activities; be able to independently acquire new knowledge, work on themselves and organize their work on a scientific basis; have a scientific idea and belief about a healthy lifestyle and the need to adhere to it, and have the training and skills to physically train themselves [6, p. 47]

To achieve good results, a teacher must have at least two goals: The first is to prepare teachers and the materials they work with and use:

1. Diagnosis of students' knowledge, skills and competencies.
2. The essence of the educational and upbringing process.
3. The main function of education and upbringing.
4. The main categories of didactics and upbringing.

5. Cooperation between teacher and student in the educational and upbringing process.

The subject, goals and objectives of the discipline of pedagogical skills, provides an opportunity to thoroughly master general information, knowledge, skills and qualifications about pedagogical skills [6,

p. 47]. Also, issues of teacher skills in school practice and in the history of pedagogical thought, pedagogical skills, communicative skills of the teacher, culture of communication and psychological activity of the student, pedagogical techniques and methods of its formation, teacher skills in the lesson and in the educational process, scientific foundations of the organization of teacher work, gaining pedagogical experience, research methods; advanced pedagogical ideas, development of experiments and ways of their implementation in modern educational institutions, history of the development of pedagogical skills, independent professional development and self-control in the educational process. It provides initial information on the skills of pedagogical communication, pedagogical experience and its application, and the study and analysis of the foundations of oriental culture of communication in teacher activity. The subject of pedagogical skills teaches the development of high-level pedagogical activity, the mastery of pedagogical techniques, as well as the experience, civic and professional status of the pedagogical person. The subject of “Pedagogical skills” together with the subjects “Theory and History of Pedagogy”, “Youth Pedagogy and Psychology”, “Methodology of Educational Work”, “Pedagogical Technologies” creates a system of knowledge and skills. The purpose of the subject of pedagogical skills is to teach the future teacher to deal with current problems in the field of pedagogy, knowledge and skills about the personality and profession of a teacher, and a creative attitude to the educational system, socio-pedagogical ideas, and educational content at each historical stage. The subject of pedagogical skills is the education of teachers who are knowledgeable, morally clean, spiritually mature, and physically healthy, based on the requirements of the Law "On Education" [5, p. 18].

In conclusion, one of the main directions of developing life skills in schoolchildren and setting life goals is to form life skills in future educators. Therefore, it is very important for future educators to have their own independent thinking and self-management. To form life skills in them, training them in a profession, raising them to be hardworking, patient, determined and diligent will be very useful in setting life goals in students. At the same time, the ability to use modern technologies for independent activities should also be developed. Reading more fiction is one of the main criteria.

Literature:

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